

Patient Satisfaction with In-Patient Hospital Services in Public and Private Hospitals in Borama, Northwest Somalia

Author's Details:

Sahardid Hussein Ibrahim¹, Hilal Mohamed Nor¹, Abdirahman Dahir Wais², Xiaomei Li^{1*}

¹ Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xi'an, China ² Amoud University, Borama, Somalia

Corresponding author;

Prof. Xiaomei Li, Dean and Professor School of Nursing, Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xian, PR, China.

Email: roselee8825@126.com

Abstract

Background: Patient satisfaction is an individualized perception resulting from the person's assessment towards the experience of the healthcare services provided. It is a key indicator to evaluate quality of healthcare. Satisfaction studies were less addressed in the continent compared to the other developing countries. This study is the first of its kind conducted in Somalia.

Objective: This study aims to assess the level of patient satisfaction with inpatient healthcare services in public and private hospitals in Borama.

Method: A cross-sectional study design was conducted from 11 July to 5th September 2019 at Borama regional hospital and Allaale hospital. Convenience sampling method was applied to recruit 270 patients as participants. A standardized structured questionnaire cited from similar literature was used to assess the level of patient satisfaction towards inpatient hospital services. SPSS version 13 were applied for data input and analysis.

Results: A total of 250 inpatients completed the study. We observed overall net inpatient satisfaction mean score of 3.91 ± 0.83 on private hospital and 2.64 ± 1.19 on public hospital. Dimensions of Medical Care 4.03 ± 0.84 and Information 3.12 ± 1.26 were found to have the highest and the lowest proportion of satisfaction in private hospital, while Discharge and Aftercare 2.51 ± 1.18 and Information 2.27 ± 1.12 remains the highest and the lowest satisfaction scores in public hospital. Multivariate analysis of socio-demographic characteristics, older groups have higher satisfaction than others ($p < 0.05$), while females have higher satisfaction on information dimension. Students, middle income groups and urban resident remain higher satisfaction on most of the satisfaction dimensions ($p < 0.05$). Patients in private hospital remains higher satisfaction scores in all evaluated dimensions compared to patients hospitalized in public hospital.

Conclusion: Generally, patients were satisfied with the hospital services acquired, with a higher satisfaction level on private hospital. Higher levels of satisfaction were found in the dimensions of admission procedure, nursing care and medical care, while lower were noted in the dimensions of information delivery, patient autonomy and discharge and aftercare, especially in public hospital. It is suggested that hospitals should take improvement measures concerning organization and management in order to deliver quality health services, improve patient satisfaction and take their competitive role in the country's healthcare services.

Keywords: In-patient Hospital Services, Satisfaction, Public Hospital, Private Hospital

Background

Proper and well-functioning hospitals are able to provide quality and effective care to their patients. In order to achieve better quality of healthcare, patient feedbacks towards the quality of care should be evaluated. Patient satisfaction has become an essential factor one of the five to assess quality of healthcare services by the World Health Organization (WHO), it is recognized a key indicator in terms of healthcare quality and patient centered care[1].

Patient satisfaction tends to have greater attention in the developing nations not only that the concept measures the quality of care but also part of effective care[2]. Patient satisfaction was applied a lot in the field of healthcare for assessing whether the accessible and quality health services were given to the patients' and maintained their healthcare desires. This concept was used widely in the healthcare market around the world. It's a key indicator of health services quality and has its influence on patient's level of recovery[3-5]. Measuring patient satisfaction towards medical services is very essential for assessing the total satisfaction of the healthcare services provided by the hospitals[6-8], and to determine whether patient's needs and expectations are accomplished, this can improve healthcare providers to organize appropriate medical interventions for their patients[9]. Patient satisfaction is a main aspect of healthcare system mainly in the developing nations [10]. Studies on this concept clearly mention that satisfied patients are more eager to have better relationship with their nurses which promote better quality of care[11, 12]. Patient satisfaction is not a pre-existing concept that can be measured but it is a phenomena based on personal judgement and evaluation that reflects their knowledge based on specific services provided. The practical definition of patient satisfaction would be the level to which patient expected goals have been accomplished[13]. Stating this, if patients acquired poor healthcare services which is not fit for their expectations then they will be dissatisfied and on the contrary, if patient experiences services that is fit or beyond their expectations they will remain satisfied[14, 15]. Monitoring and evaluating patient perspective allows patients to actively take part their own care, understand the healthcare process and involve their treatments decisions which lets them to trust their healthcare providers, follow treatment plans and feel that they have a sense of responsibility on managing and controlling their healthcare problems and promoters. Many studies show that the concept signifies a lot about the quality of healthcare and increased patient satisfaction is highly linked on treatment compliance and future use of the healthcare services delivered by hospitals[6, 16-18]. As private hospitals are becoming more dominant, healthcare institutions are experiencing an increasingly market competitions and monitoring patient satisfaction become an essential part of assessing the quality of services in the healthcare market[19]. In addition to that assessing patient satisfaction can improve and sustain the quality of these services. Furthermore, evaluating patient satisfaction are very important to the healthcare staffs to discover and assess their services level and further predict the needs of their patients as patient satisfaction and the services of care providers are interrelated[20-23]. Literature shown that patient's satisfaction towards healthcare services is affected by different factors including patient's expectations towards the services delivered and their experiences regarding to earlier services, medical staff's services quality, and the physical environmental of the hospital[24]. Recently the concept of patient satisfaction assessment was highly linked to hospital management to assess the effectiveness of patient centered care [25, 26]. Meanwhile, measuring it defines institutional achievements and the performance of the services provided[27]. Patient satisfaction sustains the hospitals image and it defines improved quality of services[28]. Studies found that patient satisfaction has positive effect on patient reliance towards services[22, 29]. This kind of positive faith can effect patient's attitude towards their healthcare provider's skillfulness and professionalism of care and treatment measures. Similarly, this positive perception will have impacted on patient's confidence towards the services trustworthiness and expertise [29]. Satisfied patients explain their medical problems to their healthcare providers while showing accurate interest on their medical conditions, able to deliver clear details of their medical issues and future health outcomes, provide medical staffs enough time to discuss diseases and its challenges it brings to their day to day life style[22, 30]. Furthermore, satisfied patients were more willing to follow any promises and medical advices delivered by their professionals. Moreover, patients will be self-encouraged to reuse the services of their medical staffs and recommend to their friends and other patients[31, 32]. However, assessment of patient satisfaction is very important in order to improve the quality of healthcare services and to our knowledge there is no related studies on this matter in the country and consequently the country's level of patient satisfaction remains unknown. Therefore, this study is aimed on measuring the level of patient satisfaction with inpatient hospital services in public and private hospitals in Borama, Northwest Somalia. This study donates evidence and knowledge practice which is very important in deciding on possible solutions and better healthcare interventions. It contributes an important understanding to the level of inpatient satisfaction and health care services and in lights

the knowledge gap, meanwhile policy makers and researchers will use it as an input source of information on patient satisfaction in this region.

Methods

Study setting This study was collected from 11th July to 5th September 2019 at Borama regional hospital (BRH) and Allaaleh hospital (AH), located in Borama town which is 120 km Northwest from Hargeisa the second largest capital of Somalia. Borama Regional Hospital is the oldest public hospital in the town and the country as a whole which is established in 1922, while the other Allaale Hospital (AH) is recently established private hospital, but the oldest of its kind and working the last 20 years. Currently both of the hospitals are teaching hospitals with a bed capacity of 357 in total with nearly a total of 263 hospital staffs. Both of the hospitals services for roughly 8,280 inpatients with different kinds of medical problems each year as report by the hospital managers.

Study design A cross sectional study design was applied in the research.

Sample and sampling method

Convenience sampling method was applied to recruit 270 patients as participants. All admitted inpatients of 270 were included in the study during the study period from 11th July to 5th September 2019. The exclusion criteria include: patients under 18 years of age, seriously ill inpatients, laboring mothers, psychiatric inpatients, patients of no informed consent, those who cannot communicate and those spend less than 24 hours in the hospitals were all excluded from the study. The patients of the medical, surgical, maternity and gynecological wards were interviewed.

Measurement tools

Based on the research requirement two set of questionnaires was applied by reviewing relevant literatures. The first questionnaire was included of basic socio-demographic characteristics of the patients including gender, age, marital status, educational level, occupation, income and address. The second questionnaire was slightly modified inpatient satisfaction questionnaire developed by Netherland Federation of University Medical Centers abbreviated as (NFU). It is a short questionnaire to measure inpatient satisfaction, based on clinical needs of in patients and it is used for numerous academic hospitals in order to compare satisfaction scores between academic hospitals. The Core Questionnaire for the assessment of Patient Satisfaction for day care (COPS-D) composed of six dimensions, each dimension in composes two, three or four questions: *Admission procedure* (2 items), *Nursing care* (2 items), *Medical care* (2 items), *Information* (4 items), *Autonomy* (3 items) and *Discharge and aftercare* (3 items). With these six dimensions a total of 16 questions included to ask inpatients in order to evaluate their perception towards the quality of healthcare services provided. Although the country does not have center for foreign language translation the study was informed to the ministry of health (MOH) and interviews was conducted by using the native trained speakers using Somali language. The reliability of each dimension of the questionnaire were tested and higher than 0.7 in Cronbach's α . Also the validity, reliability and acceptability of questionnaire has been tested for numerous articles published internationally. The answering category was scored as a 5 point Likert scale 1 (unsatisfied), 2 (somewhat satisfied), 3 (rather satisfied), 4 (quite satisfied) and 5 (very satisfied). In order to find the total mean scores, all the items in each dimension should be added and divided the resulting total score by the number of items. The overall inpatient satisfaction was assessed by asking one question in the questionnaire stating "How would you rate your overall satisfaction level regarding to the health services you received from the hospital?" A mean score of 3 or less were considered as an indicator of low satisfaction. A total mean score of 3 (rather satisfied) was considered as poor satisfaction as patients may unsure or afraid to state their level of satisfaction. The questionnaire was filled to the inpatients while they were in the hospital in order to avoid external influence or distraction. Additionally, patients had been asked to rate their overall health and overall satisfaction towards hospital services and care. Finally patients were asked to rate their hospital and whether they will recommend

the hospitals to others e.g. family members, friends and relatives and all these additional questions the same answering category were used, 5 point Likert scale^[33-36].

Data collection method and participation

The in-patients were interviewed by using structured questionnaire. Patients were recruited according to their willing and interest to take part the study. Consent sheets were delivered to patients explaining the main purpose of the study and their individual informed written consent was obtained and each of the patients were fully explained to the questions to be asked. Face to face interviews were conducted by native speakers asking patients their feedback and satisfaction towards the hospital services they acquired. All admitted patients who met the inclusion criteria were included in the sample during study period. The data was collected by twenty medical students.

Data quality and its assurance

A complete team was made by identifying clear aims and methods of the study. Training was given to the data collectors by the researcher in order to insure and understand the roles, responsibilities and aims of the study. The acceptability and understandability of the questionnaire to the participants, culture and religion was examined. Ongoing monitoring, supervision and checking the completeness of the questionnaire were done on daily basis by the researcher. All the information and data input were checked before final analysis.

Analysis and processing of data

SPSS version 13 statistical package was applied for data entry and analysis. Data input were checked and cleaning by monitoring the normal distribution of data was done by the researcher before final analysis. Demographic characteristics were analyzed descriptively. Independent *t* test was used in order to test the hypothesis and the significance. Multivariate analysis was also applied in order to explore sociodemographic factors affecting patient satisfaction in both hospitals, all statistical methods were performed under the alpha of 0.05.

Results

A total of 270 questionnaires were distributed, with 250 with valid questionnaire received, making a valid response rate of 92.5%.

Socio-demographic data of the participants

The participants mean age were 36.61 ± 16.76 ranging from 18 to 65 years and above, 160 (64%) of the participants were females, the majority of them 177 (70.8%) were married. In terms of educational level 129 (51.6%) of the participants were in no formal education, majority of participants 80 (32%) mention that they have other duties in terms of occupation and most of them 176 (70.4%) were urban residents. The results indicate that majority of patients 130 (52.0%) remain in the hospital more than three days and of them 206 (82.4%) were self-pay, while most of them 107 (42.8%) were in medical ward. Further demographic characteristics were presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of participants (n = 250)

Variables	Category	n (%)
Sex	Male	90 (36.0)
	Female	160 (64.0)
Age (yrs) (36.61± 16.76)	18-24	39 (15.6)
	25-44	110 (44.0)
	45-64	71 (28.4)
	≥ 65	30 (12.0)
Marital Status	Single	64 (25.6)

	Married	177 (70.8)
	Single mothers	9 (3.6)
Educational Status	No formal education	129 (51.6)
	Primary School	72 (28.8)
	Secondary School	30 (12.0)
	Higher Education	19 (7.6)
Occupation	Government Employee	34 (13.6)
	Merchant	40 (16.0)
	Famer	46 (18.4)
	Student	50 (20.0)
	Others	80 (32.0)
Address	Urban	176 (70.4)
	Rural	74 (29.6)
Period of Hospital Stay	1 day	45 (18.0)
	1-3 days	75 (30.0)
	>3 days	130 (52.0)
Payment Status	Self-Pay	206 (82.4)
	Free	44 (17.6)
Income	<\$ 500	198 (79.2)
	\$500-1000	36 (14.4)
	\$1100-1900	14 (5.6)
	≥\$ 2000	2 (0.8)
Type of Visit	New	182 (72.8)
	Repeat	68 (27.2)
Ward	Medical	107 (42.8)
	Surgical	88 (35.2)
	Maternity	17 (6.8)
	Gynecology	38 (15.2)

The inpatient satisfaction on health care of both hospitals

The mean scores relevant to the 16 items of satisfaction dimension lay between 4.05 (Doctor attention to patient) and 2.86 (Information transfer within healthcare staffs) to 2.53 (Information about further treatment) and 2.18 (Information by doctors) respectively. Among the six satisfaction dimensions the highest mean score of Allaale Hospital was (4.03) belonged to the medical care and the lowest mean score of it was (3.12) dealing with the information dimension, while Borama Regional Hospital the dimension with the highest mean score was (2.51) belonged to the discharge and aftercare and the one remain the lowest mean score (2.27) related to information on services dimension (Table 2). Additional questions were used in the study, including *overall health* of the patient, patient's *overall satisfaction* of hospitals services, weather patients will *recommend hospitals* to their friends and family members and finally to *rate hospital* services. The highest mean score of these four items was (4.03) belonged to the recommendation of hospital and (2.70) related to overall health respectively. The mean score of overall satisfaction was (3.91) in Allaale and (2.64) in Borama Regional Hospital Table 2.

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation scores of services dimensions and patient satisfaction (n=250)

Dimensions/Items	Allaale Hospital (AH) Mean $\bar{x} \pm SD$	Borama Regional Hospital (BRH) $\bar{x} \pm SD$	t-test	P value
Admission Procedure	3.98 ± 0.81	2.31 ± 1.11	-13.44	0.000
Reception	3.97 ± 0.84	2.34 ± 1.15	-12.80	0.000
Admission	3.99 ± 0.85	2.30 ± 1.19	-12.92	0.000

Nursing Care	4.00 ± 0.76	2.38 ± 1.12	-13.33	0.000
Nurse attention	4.00 ± 0.77	2.40 ± 1.18	-12.64	0.000
Nurse expertise	4.01 ± 0.79	2.37 ± 1.18	-12.86	0.000
Medical Care	4.03 ± 0.84	2.49 ± 1.26	-11.32	0.000
Doctor attention	4.05 ± 0.84	2.49 ± 1.26	-11.46	0.000
Doctor expertise	4.02 ± 0.86	2.50 ± 1.33	-10.69	0.000
Information	3.12 ± 1.26	2.27 ± 1.12	-5.61	0.000
Information by doctors	2.89 ± 1.56	2.18 ± 1.22	-3.96	0.000
Information by nurses	2.90 ± 1.56	2.19 ± 1.19	-4.04	0.000
Information transfer within healthcare staffs	2.86 ± 1.55	2.27 ± 1.32	-3.18	0.000
Information about speed of results (labs)	3.84 ± 1.03	2.44 ± 1.18	-9.97	0.000
Autonomy	3.25 ± 1.12	2.34 ± 1.13	-6.38	0.000
Self-sufficient	2.87 ± 1.51	2.25 ± 1.27	-3.52	0.000
Participation in treatment decisions	2.90 ± 1.53	2.29 ± 1.27	-3.45	0.000
Privacy	4.00 ± 0.73	2.50 ± 1.22	-11.75	0.000
Discharge _ Aftercare	3.72 ± 0.89	2.51 ± 1.18	-9.12	0.000
Information about further treatment	3.72 ± 0.93	2.53 ± 1.20	-8.70	0.000
Information transfer to GP	3.72 ± 0.95	2.46 ± 1.20	-9.11	0.000
Discharge procedure	3.74 ± 0.91	2.33 ± 1.16	-10.63	0.000
Overall Health	3.92 ± 0.66	2.70 ± 1.01	-11.24	0.000
Overall Satisfaction	3.91 ± 0.83	2.64 ± 1.19	-9.76	0.000
Rate Hospital	3.97 ± 0.82	2.59 ± 1.07	-11.39	0.000
Recommend of Hospital	4.03 ± 0.77	2.53 ± 1.16	-12.06	0.000

NB: The mean and the standard deviation values are organized based on Allaale Hospital (Private hospital)

Socio-demographic characteristics as predictors of patient satisfaction dimensions

Multivariate analysis was applied in order to predict the effect of socio-demographics variables on satisfaction dimensions of patients. Age was statistically significant on dimensions including admission procedure, nursing care and medical care with higher satisfaction as age increases. Gender was only related to information dimension with higher satisfaction of females than males. Marital status, length of hospital stays and type of visit was not related significantly to any of the satisfaction dimensions. The occupational and income status was related to all of the dimensions except autonomy with higher satisfaction noted on students in occupation while in income middle income class remain higher satisfaction than higher income groups. The educational status was related to information and discharge and aftercare with those lower education studies remain higher satisfaction to information dimension but not significant to discharge and aftercare. Address significantly related to admission procedure, nursing care, medical care and discharge and aftercare with urban residents remain higher scores than rural. In the autonomy dimension none of the sociodemographic variables was significant. The R^2 of each dimension was also estimated ranging from 0.098 (autonomy) to 0.22 (nursing care). Further details were shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Socio-demographic characteristics and relevant variables as predictors on satisfaction dimensions (n = 250)

	Patient satisfaction questionnaire dimensions											
	Admission Procedure		Nursing Care		Medical Care		Information		Autonomy		Discharge Aftercare	
	β Coef	P value	β Coef	P value	β Coef	P value	β Coef	P value	β Coef	P value	β Coef	P value
R ²	0.214		0.221		0.209		0.20		0.098		0.156	
Age (years)												
18-24	-0.09	0.777	-0.10	0.751	-0.05	0.861	-0.46	0.151	-0.05	0.876	-0.003	0.993
25-44†	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
45-64	0.46	0.018	0.35	0.065	0.36	0.072	0.25	0.189	0.26	0.187	0.13	0.492
≥ 65	0.18	0.503	0.67	0.012	0.72	0.011	0.42	0.121	0.26	0.350	0.31	0.239
Gender												
Male†	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Female	0.20	0.259	0.20	0.239	0.25	0.166	0.35	0.046	0.28	0.115	0.16	0.334
Marital status												
Married†	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Single	0.32	0.173	0.17	0.445	0.17	0.471	0.38	0.107	0.04	0.845	0.15	0.507
Single mothers	0.21	0.624	0.25	0.541	0.30	0.488	0.41	0.329	0.21	0.623	0.10	0.796
Occupation												
Student	1.17	0.001	1.09	0.002	1.04	0.004	1.16	0.001	0.33	0.352	0.70	0.040
Government employee†	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Merchant	0.008	0.040	-0.04	0.867	-0.12	0.680	0.09	0.749	-0.10	0.715	0.13	0.645
Famer	0.70	0.979	0.40	0.224	0.53	0.128	0.84	0.013	0.48	0.164	0.51	0.126
Others	0.12	0.643	-0.03	0.903	0.08	0.755	0.49	0.066	0.18	0.488	0.19	0.461
Income												
<\$500†	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
\$500-1000	0.55	0.019	0.57	0.012	0.51	0.035	0.48	0.040	0.34	0.154	0.66	0.004
\$1100-1900	0.57	0.100	0.46	0.168	0.63	0.077	-0.06	0.859	0.53	0.129	0.26	0.442
≥\$ 2000	1.10	0.218	1.20	0.166	0.87	0.344	-0.97	0.277	1.11	0.222	0.85	0.326
Educational Status												
No formal education†	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Primary education	-0.29	0.203	-0.24	0.281	-0.08	0.712	-0.37	0.105	0.11	0.624	0.01	0.958
Secondary education	0.17	0.510	0.20	0.446	0.22	0.414	0.73	0.007	0.30	0.274	0.51	0.052
Higher education	-0.19	0.553	-0.29	0.349	-0.41	0.224	-0.003	0.992	-0.12	0.704	-0.19	0.542
Address												
Urban	0.63	0.004	0.49	0.021	0.50	0.027	0.29	0.184	0.40	0.072	0.41	0.056
Rural†	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Length of hospital stay (days)												
1 day†	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
1-3 days	0.06	0.357	0.04	0.854	0.04	0.843	0.05	0.829	-0.16	0.506	-0.15	0.501
>3 days	0.27	0.172	0.23	0.277	0.28	0.203	0.31	0.146	0.32	0.884	0.21	0.310
Type of visit												
New†	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Repeated	0.16	0.789	0.02	0.898	0.04	0.834	-0.006	0.975	0.14	0.440	0.11	0.531
Payment status												
Self-Pay†	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
Free	0.30	0.214	0.41	0.058	0.13	0.561	0.38	0.081	0.26	0.249	0.18	0.407

† = Reference category

Discussion

According to our knowledge this study is the first of its kind that assess the level of satisfaction of hospitalized patients in both public and private hospitals in Borama, and the country as a whole. The results of this study will provide a very significant information about how patients are satisfied with the quality of care they consume, and the sociodemographic characteristics that affect their satisfaction level. In general, this study found that patients have an overall satisfaction with healthcare services they received but private hospital have higher satisfaction mean score of 3.91 compared to public mean of 2.64. This finding is consistent with the results of several studies[37-39]. We examined how familiarity of the patients with their physician during admission affects their satisfaction level. Patients feel more confident and satisfied while they are familiar with the physician they were communicating to, this promotes patient-physician interaction and increases information sharing [40]. Similar finding was noted on our study which finds significant positive relationship on patient satisfaction and familiarity. Nursing expertise and attitude during care process was related to patient satisfaction, the less of medical errors, good attitude of care and communication increases patient's level of satisfaction. The attitude and knowledge towards nursing care has been found to have statistically significant effect on patient's level of satisfaction in this study. This result is in accordance with previous finding which noted the impact of nursing care on patient satisfaction [41, 42]. Similar to nurses, doctor-patient relationship is essential, the lower the patient satisfaction with physician the lower the overall satisfaction of the patient, doctor's attitude and knowledge has a significant impact on patient satisfaction specially in terms of interpersonal communication during care. Similar results were proposed by Tung and Chang, doctor's behaviors of communication and knowledge have a significant impact on patient satisfaction and can affect their health outcomes[42, 43]. Although higher mean was found in private hospital, the information dimension remains the lowest satisfaction score of both hospitals in this study, similar conclusions were reported by Kabatooro in Uganda[40]. The higher satisfaction of private in this dimension can be the possibility that private invites less number of patients compared to public hospital which may give medical staffs time to communicate to their patients. According to research giving appropriate information about the causes of the disease and the preventable measures has been linked to higher satisfaction, acceptance of provided medical advices and valuable health outcomes compared to those who don't. [44]. Patient autonomy and their participation in care is related to information sharing and indeed patients expressed less satisfaction which means that they have not been given enough opportunity for their participation towards treatment decisions which resulted a decrease on patient satisfaction level in our study, nurses should put on emphasis of patient information and autonomy and consider this as their primary rights although it can be impacted by the time and workload of nurses. Similar conclusions were found on study in Cyprus which found that patient autonomy was related to patient satisfaction[45]. Keeping patient privacy and conversations during medical examinations was related to higher patient satisfaction in this study which is in line with study of Billing in 2007[46] which underlines the importance of keeping patient secret and examining them in private environment. During discharge procedure process patient's informational needs about future care and further treatment plans and medical transfer instructions should be met. Lack of proper information and consultations after discharged can bring lots of dissatisfaction and may put patient's life at risk. Our study finds a significant impact on discharge and aftercare information on patient satisfaction level which incorporates with earlier studies of this concept[47, 48].

In our study patients were asked to rate their overall health by asking "how would you rate your overall health"? on 5-point scale from a category of 1 *critical* and 5 *excellent* the mean score found was higher of patients in the private hospital, whose rated their overall health as good, very good or excellent compared to public, the possible explanation of this is that private hospitals may have better equipment and less workload than public which gives some trust to its patients, but this feedback can be associated with the sociodemographic characteristics such as age of patients as specific age group may find more special care than others which remain them to be grateful to the services given. [49]. Similarly, patients were asked a question on assessing the overall satisfaction regarding to the services provided "how would you rate your overall

satisfaction regarding to the health services”? although patients were generally satisfied with services of both hospitals higher overall satisfaction were noted from patients in private hospital compared to public which is similar results reported by Charalambous in Cyprus[39]. Patients were given the opportunity to rate their hospital from *1 being the worst* and *5 being the best hospital*, patients in the private hospital rate their hospital higher than public, this rating reflects the overall services of the hospital, the finding in lines with a study in Turkey by Tengilimoglu[50]. According to the literature, patient’s preference to visit hospital can be the result of recommendation from friends or family members[51], this concept were also evaluated in our study, patients were asked “*would you recommended this hospital to your family and friends*”? statistically significant mean difference were found between hospitals, patients in private hospital mention incase for future medical use they will visit the same hospital, this is as a result of higher satisfaction from the services they got from private hospital. The results of this study shows that patients choose hospitals by the recommendations given to their pervious hospitalized friends or family members. These results were similar with previous studies which mentioned that increased satisfaction can promote hospitals recommendations [52].

In terms of sociodemographic characteristics our study finds that age, gender, occupation, income, educational level and address was significantly associated with the scores of the six satisfaction dimensions in the questionnaires. Like previous studies we find that older patients tend to have higher satisfaction compared to younger, this is significant in three dimensions[53]. Gender although some studies mention higher satisfaction in men than women[54]. but in our study it only related to the information dimension which results that females have higher satisfaction scores than males[55]. We studied the influence of occupation and income of our patients’ satisfaction level which were significantly associated five of the six dimensions. The impact of individual’s income on quality and services of healthcare remains significant, another study recently published in Lancet suggests that increased out of pocket in hospital services are related to higher level of dissatisfaction[56]. Although studies examined the effect of income on patient’s satisfaction resulted mixed findings, but patients with low socioeconomic level has less expectation compared to the higher income and remain more satisfied in healthcare services. Similar finding was noted in this study, patients with lower level income or those in middle income remains higher satisfaction compared to their higher income groups[57, 58]. Patients who have higher employment would always have higher expectations and more demanding from their clinicians which remains them to be poorly satisfied compared to their counterparts. In this study the association between occupation and patient satisfaction was statistically significant and was only limited to student patients which tend to have higher satisfaction scores than other occupation categories, this is as a result from income related occupation with higher job related to poor satisfaction[59, 60]. Interestingly there were no significantly association among income and occupations with the regard to autonomy dimension. Similarly, we have studied the effect of educational level on patient satisfaction and it was related significantly to information dimension with those no education or lower level of studies remains higher satisfaction score than others, this can be a reason for those with higher education might have the ability to understand the working environment in the clinics, while on the opposite those with lower level might not familiar enough about things related to care which can easily make them satisfied. Similar conclusions were found by other researches[61, 62]. According the studies place of residence can be related to patient satisfaction, in our study we find that living in rural or urban were related significantly to four satisfaction dimensions as displayed in the result table 3, but unlike other researches which mention that rural patients were found to be more satisfied than urban[63]. We find that urban residents remain higher satisfaction than rural residence this can be due to the economical difference between those two residential places or the distance when visiting hospitals for medical services. Finally, we also explored the effect of marital status, length of hospital stays and type of visit, but we did not find that these variables had any significant influence on patient satisfaction dimensions which is similar conclusions with Romero in 2019[64].

Limitations of the study

It is essential for hospital managers, healthcare providers and policy makers to observe the actual practice of medical care within the hospital. However, it worth noting to discover on the first time the significant difference between those two hospitals in this study. This results may contribute to a credible value of information on the level of patient satisfaction and factors that influence it, analyze the possible weakness and design strategies for improvement and policy changes. The study is highly site-specific which may limit its generality, since patients were interviewed in the hospital setting, it is possible that they give responses favoring the care provider which results social desirability bias.

Conclusion

To our knowledge this study is the first of its kind ever conducted in the area and the country as a whole assessing the satisfaction level of patients in public and private hospitals in Borama, Northern Somalia. This cross sectional study observed a level of satisfaction on patients in both hospitals, but an increased levels of satisfaction were noted in private than in public hospital. The study highlights that patient satisfaction should not be viewed as a separate variable. Factors including quality of care, medical staff attitude, information delivery, services responsiveness, privacy, recommendation from relatives and friends are all essential on enhancing patient's use of medical services in hospitals. As previous studies, we found some of the sociodemographic characteristics have significant effect on patient's level of satisfaction.

Recommendations

The hospital administration system should first work on implementing new measures that improve the administration system, quality of care, information delivery, attitude of medical and nursing staffs, hospital stay and discharge, self-sufficient and privacy service in order to increase patient satisfaction. Hospital staffs including physicians and nurses should best work on improving patient health education about medical conditions, treat with respect, communication and maintain proper interaction between them and their patients. Fresh leadership and hospital reformation with modern management system that would work on improving patient satisfaction should have to be in placed especially in public hospitals. As public hospitals are the primary referrals and expected to invite a large number of patients' proper appointments should be scheduled in order to give proper time to patients during admission and consultation. Hospital managers should have to remain their offices rather than running their personal clinics during work time, and to hire professional hospital managers rather than clinical doctor as a manager. Efforts should be in placed by administrators in order to use effectively on the resources and government funds, by emphasizing areas that need improvements and patients are less satisfied. Proper healthcare reforms should have to be in placed by the government and specific areas should be assigned to individuals with specific knowledge related areas. Patient satisfaction should always be reviewed and researched for quality improvements. Furtherer studies should be done on areas involving policy changes on patient satisfaction and socio-demographic characteristics and its effect on patient satisfaction.

List of abbreviations

WHO: World Health Organization

NFU: Netherland Federation of University Medical Centers

COPS-D: Core Questionnaire for the assessment of Patient Satisfaction for day care

MOH: Ministry of Health

Ethical approval and consent to participate

To conduct the study, ethical approval was taken from the ethical committee of Health Sciences Center of Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xi'an, China. Similarly, ethical clearance was also obtained from the ethical and management committee of both hospitals studied which were under the Ministry of Health (MOH). The patients and the administrative of selected wards were asked permissions and their informed written consent were

obtained from each patient and they were told that their information is strictly confidential and only used for research purpose.

Availability of data and materials

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Authors 'contributions

SHI contributed to the overall design, analysis and data interpretation. XL supervised and provided inputs in study design and methodology. HMN and ADW were responsible for recruitment of study participants and supervision of data collection. SHI wrote the first draft of the manuscript which all the authors revised and approved for submission. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank to the hospitals managers and staffs who permitted as to do this research in their institutions. Importantly we acknowledge and appreciate to all patients for their corporation and take part of this study.

Author details

¹ Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xian, PR, China. ²Amoud University Borama, Somalia.

References

- i. *Silbertstein N. Are patients' satisfaction surveys a good idea? Podiatry Management. Academic Journal. 2010; 29(03):113.*
- ii. *Camgoz-Akdag H, Zineldin M. The quality of health care and patient satisfaction an exploratory investigation of the 5Qs model at Republic of Kazakhstan. International Journal of Health Care Quality Assurance, in press. 2010.*
- iii. *Sun BC, Adams JG, Burstin HR. Validating a model of patient satisfaction with emergency care. Ann Emerg Med. 2001;38:527–532.*
- iv. *Sahin B, Yilmaz F, Lee, KH. Factors affecting inpatient satisfaction: structural equation modeling. J Med Syst. 2007;31:9–16.*
- v. *Xavier-Yves Zendjidjian, Karine Baumstarck, Pascal Auquier, Anderson Loundou, Christophe Lançon, Laurent Boyer. Satisfaction of hospitalized psychiatry patients: why should clinicians care? Patient Prefer Adherence. 2014;8:575-83.*
- vi. *Wagner D, Bear M. Patient satisfaction with nursing care: a concept analysis within a nursing framework. J Adv Nurs. 2009;65(3):692–701.*
- vii. *Darega B, D N, Letimo T, Hunde T, Hayile Y, Yeshitla S, Amare M. Perceived quality of nursing cares practices in inpatient departments of bale zone hospitals, Oromiya regional state, Southeast Ethiopia facility -based cross sectional study. Qual Prim Care. 2016;24(1)39–45.*
- viii. *F Hughes. Nurses at the forefront of innovation. Int Nurs Rev. 2006;53(2)94–101.*
- ix. *Tang WM, S.C.-Y, Lim WC. Patient satisfaction with nursing care: a descriptive study using interaction model of client health behavior. International Journal of Nursing Science. 2013;3(2)51–6.*
- x. *Shinde M, and Kapurkar K. Patient's satisfaction with nursing care provided in selected areas of tertiary care hospital. International Journal of Science and Research. 2014;3(2)150–61.*

- xi. Aharony L, Strasser S. *Patient satisfaction: what we know about and what we still need to explore. Medical care review.*1993;50(1)49-79.
- xii. Aldaqal SM, Alghamdi H, AlTurki H, El-deek BS, Kensarah A. *Determinants of patient satisfaction in the surgical ward at a University Hospital in Saudi Arabia. Life Science Journal.* 2012;9(1)277-80.
- xiii. *The Health Boards Executive Measurement of patient satisfaction guideline 2. Health Strategy Implementation Project, Ireland.* 2003;37.
- xiv. Ahmadi Kashkoli S, Zarei E, Daneshkohan A, Khodakarim S. *Hospital responsiveness and its effect on overall patient satisfaction: a cross-sectional study in Iran. Int J Health Care Qual Assur.* 2017;30(8):728-36.
- xv. Combs HW, Laohasirichaikul B, Chaipoopirutana S. *Effective customer relationship management of health care: a study of hospitals in Thailand. J Manag Mark Res.* 2011;6:1.
- xvi. De Silva A, Valentine N. *Measuring responsiveness: Results of a key informant survey in 35 countries. In: GPE Discussion Paper Series. World Health Organization., 2000;21(Geneva.).*
- xvii. Wood F. *In-patient Psychiatric Patients. Journal of Advanced Nursing* 2006;55:655-663.
- xviii. *OECD, Health at a Glance OECD Indicators, OECD Publishing, 2013.*
- xix. Net N, Sermsri S, Chompikul J. *Patient satisfaction with Health Services at the Out-Patient Department Clinic of Wangmamyen Community Hospital, Sakeao Province, Thailand. J Public Health.* 2007;5(2):34.
- xx. Peprah AA. *Determinants of patients' satisfaction at Sunyani regional hospital, Ghana. Int J Bus Soc Res.* 2014;4(1):96-108.
- xxi. Garratt AM, Solheim E, and Danielsen K. *National and Cross-National Surveys of Patient Experiences: A Structured Review.* 2008.
- xxii. Alrubaiee L, Alkaa'ida F. *The mediating effect of patient satisfaction in the patients' perceptions of healthcare quality-patient trust relationship. Int J Market Stud.* 2011;3(1):103.
- xxiii. Qadri SS, Pathak R, Singh M, Ahluwalia S, Saini S, Garg P. *An assessment of patients satisfaction with services obtained from a tertiary care hospital in rural Haryana. Int J Collab Res Inter Med Publ Health.* 2012;4.(8):1524-37.
- xxiv. Ko HH, Zhang H, Telford JJ, Enns R. *Factors influencing patients' satisfaction when undergoing endoscopic procedures. Gastrointest Endosc.* 2009;69:883-91.
- xxv. Smith M, E B. *Developing tools to assess client satisfaction at district hospital Technical Report.* 2001.
- xxvi. Webster TR, Mantopoulos J, Jackson E, Cole-Lewis H, Kidane L, Kebede S, et al. *A brief questionnaire for assessing patient healthcare experiences in low-income settings. International J Qual Health Care.* 2011;23:(3):258-68.
- xxvii. Boshoff C, Gray B. *The relationships between service quality, customer satisfaction and buying intentions in the private hospital industry. South Afr J Bus Manag.* 2004;35(4):27-37.
- xxviii. Syed Saad A. *Determinants of customer satisfaction with hospitals: a managerial model. Int J Health Care Qual Assur.* 1998;11(6):181-7.
- xxix. Moliner MA. *Loyalty, perceived value and relationship quality in healthcare services. J Serv Manag.* 2009;20(1):76-97.
- xxx. Elena A, Platonova Richard M, Shewchuk. *Patient assessment of primary care physician communication: segmentation approach. Int J Health Care Qual Assur.* 2015;28(4):332-42.
- xxxi. Zarei E, Mohammad A, Mahmoud Ghazi Tabatabaei S, Rashidian A, Rahimi Forushani A, Khabiri R. *Understanding patients' behavioral intentions: evidence from Iran's private hospitals industry. J Health Organ Manag.* 2014;28(6):795-810.
- xxxii. Moher D, Sullivan K. *A guide to direct measures of patient satisfaction in clinical practice. CMAJ.* 1992;147(7):989.
- xxxiii. Kleefstra SM, K R, Veldkamp CM, Winters-van der Meer ACM, Mens MA, Blijham GH, de Haes JC. *A core questionnaire for the assessment of patient satisfaction in academic hospitals in The Netherlands: development and first results in a nationwide study. QualSaf Health Care* 2010;19(5):24.

- xxxiv. Enwirda-Kromdijk GJCM, B G, Veldkamp CM, de Haes JC. *De ontwikkeling van een Kernvragenlijst Klanttevredenheid ten behoeve van patienttevredenheidsonderzoek in academische ziekenhuizen [The development of a core questionnaire patient satisfaction for research in academic hospitals]*. NFU, Utrecht. 2002.
- xxxv. Kleefstra S, et al. *An instrument assessing patient satisfaction with day care in hospitals*. *BMC Health Services Research*. 2012;12(1):125.
- xxxvi. Kleefstra SM, et al. *Trends in patient satisfaction in Dutch university medical centers: room for improvement for all*. *BMC Health Services Research*. 2015;15(1):112.
- xxxvii. Sharma SK, Kamra P. *Patient satisfaction with Nursing Care in Public and Private Hospitals*. *International Journal of Nursing Care*. 2013;1(2):134-9.
- xxxviii. Jadoo SAA, Puteh S, Ahmed Z, Jawdat A. *Level of patients' satisfaction toward National Health Insurance in Istanbul City-Turkey*. *BMC Public Health*. 2012;12 Suppl 2:A5.
- xxxix. Charalambous M, Giannis & Talias, Michael. *Assessment of Patients' Satisfaction with Care Provided in Public and Private Hospitals of the Republic of Cyprus: A Comparative Study*. *International Journal of Caring Sciences*. 2018;11(1):125.
- xl. Kabatooro, A, Fred Ndoboli, and Namatovu J. *Patient satisfaction with medical consultations among adults attending Mulago hospital assessment centre*. *South African family practice : official journal of the South African Academy of Family Practice/Primary Care*. 2016;58(3):87-93.
- xli. Desai, V. V. "Case study: Patient satisfaction and service quality dimensions,". *Journal of Advances Management*. 2011;4:40-45.
- xlvi. Chen H, et al. *Factors influencing inpatients' satisfaction with hospitalization service in public hospitals in Shanghai, People's Republic of China*. *Patient Prefer Adherence*. 2016;10:469-77.
- xlvi. Tung Y-C, Chang G-M. *Patient satisfaction with and recommendation of a primary care provider: associations of perceived quality and patient education*. *Int J Qual Health Care*. 2009;21(3):206-213.
- xlv. Wright, Steven M, et al. *Patient satisfaction of female and male users of veterans health administration services*. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*. 2006;21(3):S26-S32.
- xlv. Merkouris, A, et al. *Assessment of patient satisfaction in public hospitals in Cyprus: A descriptive study*. *Health Science Journal*. 2013;7:28-40.
- xlvi. Billing K, N.H., Selva D. *Improving patient satisfaction through information provision*. *Clin Experiment Ophthalmol*. 2007;35(5):439-47.
- xlvi. Maloney, Lynn R, Marianne E, and Weiss. *Patients' Perceptions of Hospital Discharge Informational Content*. *Clinical Nursing Research*. 2008;17(3):200-219.
- xlvi. Koelling, Todd M, et al. *Discharge education improves clinical outcomes in patients with chronic heart failure*. *Circulation*. 2005;111(2):179-85.
- xlix. Bowling A. "An "inverse satisfaction law"? Why don't older patients criticise health services?," *J Epidemiol Community Health*. 2002;56:482.
- l. Tengilimoglu D, Kisa A, and Dziegielewski S.F. *Patient Satisfaction in Turkey: Differences between Public and Private Hospitals*. *Journal of Community Health*. 1999;24(1):73-91.
- li. Bamfo, B. and Dogbe C. *Factors influencing the choice of private and public hospitals: empirical evidence from Ghana*. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Healthcare Marketing*. 2017;11:80-96.
- lii. Makarem J, et al. *Patients' satisfaction with inpatient services provided in hospitals affiliated to Tehran University of Medical Sciences, Iran, during 2011-2013*. *Journal of medical ethics and history of medicine*. 2016;9:6.
- liii. He Xin, Li, Lingui, Bian Y. *Satisfaction survey among primary health care outpatients in the backward region: An empirical study from rural Western China*. *Patient Prefer. Adherence*. 2018;12:1989-1996.
- liv. Liu X, Lu H, Wang Y, Wang W, Hou Z, Tan A, Mao, Z. *Factors affecting patient satisfaction with ecdemic medical care: A cross-sectional study in nanchang, china*. *Patient Prefer. Adherence*. 2018;12:1373-1382.

- lv. Sommet N, Morselli D. *Keep Calm and Learn Multilevel Logistic Modeling: A Simplified Three-Step Procedure Using Stata, R, Mplus, and SPSS. Int. Rev. Soc. Psychol.* 2017;30:203–218.
- lvi. X W. "Violence against doctors in China,". *Lancet.* 2014;384:745.
- lvii. Yu W, Li M, Xue C, Wang J, Liu J, Chen H, Zhang L. *Determinants and influencing mechanism of outpatient satisfaction: A survey on tertiary hospitals in the People's Republic of China. Patient Prefer. Adherence.* 2016;10:601-612.
- lviii. Vuong Q-H. *Sociodemographic Factors Influencing Vietnamese Patient Satisfaction with Healthcare Services and Some Meaningful Empirical Thresholds. Iranian journal of public health.* 2018;47(1):119-126.
- lix. Abioye Kuteyi EA, Bello I, Olaleye TM, Ayeni IO, Amedi MI. "Determinants of patient satisfaction with physician interaction: a cross-sectional survey at the Obafemi Awolowo University Health Centre, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. " *South African Family Practice.* 2010;52:557-62.
- lx. Miao Q, Alexander N, Schwarz G, Xu L. *Servant leadership, trust, and the organizational commitment of public sector employees in China. Public Adm.* 2014;92:727-743.
- lxi. Khan AA, Siddiqui AZ, Mohsin SF, Mohamed BA. *Sociodemographic Characteristics as Predictors of Satisfaction in Public and Private Dental Clinics. Pak J Med Sci.* 2018;34(5):1152-1157.
- lxii. Hu L, Zhou B, Liu S, Wang Z, Liu Y. *Outpatient Satisfaction with Tertiary Hospitals in China: The Role of Sociodemographic Characteristics. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health.* 2019;16(19):3518.
- lxiii. Yan Z, Wan D, Li L. *Patient satisfaction in two Chinese provinces: rural and urban differences. Int J Qual Health Care.* 2011;23:384-389.
- lxiv. Romero-García M, et al. *Level of satisfaction of critical care patients regarding the nursing care received: Correlation with sociodemographic and clinical variables. Australian Critical Care.* 2019;32(6):486-493.